

A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Insights from the 2024-2025 Italian field study: understanding the digital lives of Italian preadolescents

At our recent ASAP co-creation workshop (february 2025) we have presented some of the key findings from our field research in Italy, focusing on children's online safety and communication habits. ...

The research, based on **interviews, focus groups, and surveys** with students, parents, teachers, school leaders, and cyberbullying specialists, highlights key

trends, concerns, and possible solutions for a safer digital experience.

Smartphone ownership: the new normal

The study reveals that **89% of middle school students** in Italy who replied to our survey own a smartphone, and among them:

- **42% received it at age 11**
- **26% at age 10**
- **21% before age 10**

For the **11% without their own smartphone**, the majority (81%) **regularly use a family member's device**.

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